

Information Dissemination Management/ Advanced Intelligent Network

Services for Department of Defense

Developed for MILCON 99

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ABSTRACT: *This paper will describe DISA's requirements for a Information Dissemination Management/Advanced Intelligent Network that investigates new or emerging technologies associated with DISN and other DoD transmission networks. The primary thrust to develop a conversion path for the merging of data, video, and voice transmission. A secondary goal is to improve Information Awareness/Information Assurance while reducing the need for transmission of duplicative information. Lastly, a roadmap will be developed to enable the ultimate end users to access the information in real-time with little or no wasted time and effort.*

I. Information Dissemination Management (IDM)/ Advanced Intelligent Networking (AIN) Services for the Department of

Defense: The IDM/AIN Services will describe the anticipated technology thrusts required to create a Information Dominate Infrastructure. The primary focus will be hierarchical data distribution, full use of multimedia, and convergence technology of data, video, and telephony.

Introduction: The U.S Joint Chief's of Staff released the Joint Vision 2010 (JV 2010) document in FY97 to describe and outline of goals for the U.S. Department of Defense. One of the main pillars of the program is Information Warfare (IW). One of the two primary goals of IW is Information Superiority. The JV 2010 goal for Information Superiority is:

"Improvements in the speed, accuracy, and availability of data can make the battlespace of the future fundamentally different from that of any previous era. But to sustain the flow of high quality information requires more than just an edge over an adversary. We must have

information superiority: the ability to collect, process, and disseminate an uninterrupted flow of information while exploiting or denying an adversary's ability to do the same."¹

Each day, Information Superiority is becoming more difficult. The difficulty arises in the explosive growth of the potential field of data and information. Since 1996, the Internet has been doubling in size every 120 days, personal and corporate web pages have been doubling every 45 days, new forms of data are being used, and the amount of information contained in commercial/public/private databases double every 60 days.² Being able to accurately search and retrieve all types of pertinent data can be overwhelming.

1. Goals and Objectives: The advents of new technologies to enable users of DoD Information networks are the primary focus of DISA's research and development efforts.

¹ Joint Vision 2010, October 1996, US Joint Chiefs of Staff
² Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Laboratory for Information and Decision Systems, 1997 Report on the Internet, Cambridge, Mass., 02139-4307

- a. **Network Developments:** The next generation of the DOD Backbone network must be capable of scalable services to the end-user, allow for economical enhancements, be able to classify and prioritize traffic across the backbone, edge and backbone elements must be self aware to allow active cooperation to maximize throughput/performance, resiliency, flexible, and security.
- b. **Transport Developments:** The next generation of the DOD backbone network will increasing rely on such technologies as Wave Division Multiplexing (WDM) to carry the data, Private Network-to-Network Interface (PNNI) hierarchical signaling to allow self-awareness, and convergence of data, voice and video upon the same infrastructure.
- c. **Decreased dependence on Commercial Telecommunications:** DoD has always been heavily dependent upon the offering of the commercial telecommunications (Telcos) companies. While the Telcos offer a multitude of services, the unique needs of DoD have always posed problems for the Telcos. The Telcos primary emphasis has always been the commercial users. New DoD services have been implemented slowly. DISA will invest in technologies to greatly reduce the time required to provide new services to the end users.
- d. **Site Customization:** Another thrust of the IDM/AIN efforts will attempt to improve end user's information awareness and assurance. With the explosive growth of data, the growth of information sites, and the myriad of data formats, the typical user cannot quickly locate and retrieve critical information. New technologies will be investigated that can locate data, store common data as close to the end user as

possible, index data, replicate data, and replace obsolete data quickly.

- e. **Development of Hierarchical Servers:** The future IDM/AIN includes large data warehouses, content distribution services, and video generation/transmission systems. To reduce bandwidth requirements, duplication of data, and increased user information awareness, a hierarchical set of servers are anticipated. Large multi-terabit storage servers interconnected by Wave Division Multiplexed systems to the Service Delivery Node (SDN). These Systems will collect, validate, store, and replicate data between each SDN. Secondary large servers will be located at user-side of the SDN to allow the user access and retrieval of information for local use. These secondary servers will also define the types of information stored on the large servers. Users will only have to use site bandwidth for the majority of information access.

The DISA goal is to allow users launch, monitor and control applications from inside their local network from a wide range of platforms running under general-purpose multitasking (Unix, Windows NT) operating systems with the information required by the applications being continually updated and validated by the backbone SDN.

- II. **ADVANCED INTELLIGENT NETWORK (AIN) SERVICE DELIVERY NODE:** As networks get more complex due in large part to the quantity and quality of the information being transmitted and manipulated, Network Servers must be able to handle ever increasing demands. These demands include network/switch configuration information, data, subordinate server

controls, smart agents, and bandwidth management protocols.

1. **Intelligent Servers:** In the AIN, the network WAN server (located at the SDN) will be the primary focal point for all aspects of network performance within a WAN. The network SDN server will be the central repository for all information about the WAN. (see Diagram 1, top half (SDN)).

a. **Intelligent Switching Load:** The most significant information being handled by the Network WAN server is all of the network configuration information. The Network SDN server would perform backup, configuration/protocol standardization, and site integration for all of the switches, routers/route-servers within the network. User personnel would be able go to one source for site information thus allowing system administrators to be free of the requirement of being hardware engineers.

Diagram 2: IDM/AIN Backbone SDN Configuration

b. **Intelligent Data Loads:** The Network SDN server shall allow a centralized data repository for subordinate MANs and LANs. Bandwidth reduction that may be achieved by eliminating duplicative information transmissions from multiple users/networks that require the same or similar data. The types of services that may be provided are Data Warehousing, data indexing, and data collaboration.

c. **Intelligent Video Loads:** The Network SDN server shall allow a centralized Video repository and transmission control for subordinate MANs and LANs. The potential to provide real-time, high quality video to the end-user without significantly degrading available site bandwidth. The key to real-time video is large file transfer and Bandwidth-on Demand.

2. **Smart Server:** The term Smart Server refers to the server in a LAN or workgroup that directly ties to user side of the SDN to the SDN Server. The smart server will be able to customize the data retrieved from SDN Server. The Smart Server will schedule data transfers, data base synchronization, large file transfer, and web data updates. The smart servers main function is to bring the most common set of user required data as close as possible to the user such that external communication bandwidth is optimized. The Smart Server will also reduce the access time for the user by eliminating the need for distant link data refreshing. Lastly, the Smart Server will coordinate Smart Agent requested data to again reduce the retrieval time for the user (see Diagram 1, bottom half, customer premise equipment).

3. Smart Agent: The Smart Agent is defined as any script or executable code used by an end-user that can semi-automatically retrieve and manipulate data. The Smart Agent is the individual user's primary means that enables the user to directly benefit from the Smart Server. A series of Smart Agents will be developed/tested to demonstrate and quantify the gains in productivity that can be realized from Intelligent Servers/Smart Servers hierarchy. Smart Agent shall be created by an end user based on the interface developed for the Smart Server. The Smart Server will register the Smart Agents (i.e. determine the function and output of the Smart Agent) and provide access to the data stored in the Smart Server. The Smart Agent may also be scheduled to run at certain times to allow the end user to have pre-set, updated, data packets (or when new information is available) delivered to the desktop. The next three sections describe the IDM/AIN services.

III. Telephony Services

1. Telephony Services: The concept of Intelligent Networks was initially begun in response to the convergence of data and telephone services. The future DISA networks will take advantage of the developed IN software suites.

2. Telephony IN Model: The IN offers a model for the control and invocation of services available through the network. Its elements are those parts of the network that execute IN applications. Thus, while the Signaling System (SS7) architecture describes the rules for communicating between elements, the IN model classifies relationships among the elements themselves and IN applications providing services.

The DISA goal is to allow users launch, monitor and control all telephony applications from inside the network from a wide range of platforms. The master platform will provide the

means to download application-development environments and software required implementing IN telephony applications (such as SS7 across ATM, local PBX control, and FXO operations).

3. Voice over Packet (Voice over IP/Voice over ATM): Voice over packet capability will be an additional feature of the DISA Advanced IN. The growing use of the Internet/Site Intranets/Command Extranets and the demand for more advanced data services has caused major problems in the (Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN)). The PSTN was originally designed to handle relatively short duration calls that had certain types of statistical distributions. These numbers were used to calculate how many trunks would be needed to provide service for all the customers in a region. The average call duration for a data call exceeds the design parameters of the original PSTN. The effect of this is that T1 lines that carry the calls are tied up longer, reducing the availability of service to the customers in a region as mandated by law. The only way that DOD Users can resolve this issue with TDM technology is to add more T1 lines—an expensive solution. VOP enables DOD Commands to bypass the PSTN and handle more traffic because the "circuits" used to carry it are virtual across the network, i.e., they are defined only by a logical path, virtual channel (VC), through the IDM/AIN backbone network. ATM technology provides bandwidth on demand in its packet-switched framework, so each call has its own VC through the network that can be billed based on actual payload transmitted—not a flat rate based on tying up of a physical connection. The voice samples can be sent using ATM cells, which are reliably and flexibly routed to their destination.

The basic hardware will contain the necessary software to perform VOP (VOIP/VTOA). The key to Voice over Packet (VOP) is the ability to manage both the signaling and voice portions of the packets. In most cases, VOP will require SS7 to be carried on ATM streams. The IDM/AIN

software must interface to both streams of information from the telephony network and converts them to a single stream of packets transmitted to the packet network. The hardware will be incorporated into the basic hardware suite of equipment. The software functions are divided into two general areas:

Voice packet software: This software, typically run on a DSP (part of the VOP gateway), prepares voice samples for transmission over the packet network. Its components perform tone detection and generation, echo cancellation, voice compression, voice activity detection, jitter removal, resampling, and voice packetization.

Telephony signaling gateway software: This software interacts with the telephony equipment (POTS and DSN), translating signaling into state changes used by the network protocol module (described below) to set up connections. These state changes are on-hook, off-hook, trunk seizure, etc. This software must support E&M (wink, delay and immediate), loop or ground start FXS and FXO, ISDN BRI/PRI and QSIG.

IV. DATA

- 1. Data Requirements:** The IDM/AIN efforts in data will attempt to ensure the Commander's ability to collect, process, reduce, and disseminate an uninterrupted flow of information critical to provide the "Information Center of Gravity". The goal is to provide the Commander with a clean, verified, and secure set of indexed data sets gathered from thousands of non-clean, non-secure sources without significant manpower or exhaustive data searches.
- 2. IDM/AIN Hardware:** The IDM/AIN suite of equipment will provide an autonomous set of hardware and software to identify and collect potential sources of data throughout the Internet and DOD databases. All of the filtering, automated searches, data indexing,

sorting will be performed by an equipment suite and storing all of the findings in a fast response data warehouse (the SDN Server hardware). The Commander's can access the data warehouse to provide the critical data in significantly reduced time period. No longer will information require several large areas or vehicles. Operations Centers could become as small as a laptop and a mobile communications transceiver.

- a. Data Warehousing:** The IDM/AIN demonstration equipment suite will consist of a data warehouse subsystem. The data warehouse subsystem will contain one super server with a RAID 5 mass storage device connected to high performance switches. The data warehouse software will allow the servers to access a large number of databases/textual databases and store them in one location; as a read only database, guaranteeing stability over time. Although the warehouse is capable of providing many different functions, the design focus is on the needs of the end users. The implementation of a subject in the warehouse goes through a progression of stages. The quality and usefulness of data improve through each successive stage of implementation. The stages are 1. Getting accurate detailed data within a subject area. 2. Integrating accurately detailed information among subject areas, e.g. combining Red Force TO&E data and Red Force equipment capabilities. 3. Creating useful summary, aggregate, and history information.

The uses of these types of Data Mining techniques can greatly increase the speed of data location but also reduce the shipment of unimportant data.

- b. Data Dissemination:** The last key aspect of IDM/AIN demonstration project hardware is data dissemination. The equipment suite is designed to greatly

enhance data dissemination. The data servers have been selected to be multiprocessing to allow processors to be devoted to data collection/data reduction/data mining and other processors to be used to handle customer queries. Connections to the target textual and databases are at ATM speeds. The data warehouse and data servers pass information at OC-48c (2,44 GB/sec) speeds and are being switched by 40 GB/sec ATM switches. Secondary servers will be connected by OC-12c links using 10 GB/sec switches.

V. VIDEO

1. **Video Requirements:** Video data is the fastest growing type of information being demanded by the DISN user. Video includes large graphical images, remote video feeds, commercial video (such as CNN), video teleconferencing, and distant learning. These types of data will place the largest demand on the DISN based on the size of the digitized data and the rate of data transmission. The IDM/AIN effort will invest solutions to provide more video data to the user.
2. **Streaming Video:** The vast majority of the commercial technologies being utilized for video content is streaming video functions. Streaming video is a very useful technology for non-real-time applications. The only significant problem with streaming video is the size of the file requiring transfer. The IDM/AIN will test and evaluate emerging file transfer technologies such as Multicast File Transfer Protocol (MFTP) that allows large files to be transferred seamlessly across servers using ATM or IP protocols.
3. **Real Time Video:** While streaming video technologies are acceptable for non-real time video transmission, a significant portion of the DoD mission requires real time video to the

end user. The IDM/AIN demonstration project will assess several key technologies in the area of real time video. MPEG-2 and HDTV processes will be prototyped and tested.

- a. **Full Motion Video:** The IDM/AIN demonstration project will concentrate on Motion Pictures Executive Group-2 (MPEG-2) formats for most real time video applications. Full motion video feeds will be fed into the MPEG-2 encoder and send to selected end users where PC card-based MPEG-2 decoders will provide the video display. MPEG-2 encoding rates of 3-12 MB/sec will be tested and optimal ranges based on quality trade-off(s) will be developed.
- b. **Store-and-Forward Full Motion Video:** The IDM/AIN demonstration project will also demonstrate store-and-forward of full motion video. A video encoder and software that can access the server RAID will be used within the hardware suite. Full motion video, recorded television broadcasts, and VCR tape-based video will be encoded using MPEG-2 and stored on the RAID. A Video interface will be prototyped to allow remote retrieval, automated transmission, and playback from anywhere within the network limits. Closed captioning will also be associated with the store-and-forward video to allow text miners to associate key words with video sections.
- c. **Video Teleconferencing (VTC):** The IDM/AIN demonstration project will also validate MPEG-2 Video Teleconferencing techniques. The Global Broadcast System (GBS) has been developed to use and integrate MPEG-2 video streams for transmission to those users who cannot link to traditional telecommunications systems. By developing MPEG-2 VTC

capabilities, the VTC outputs can be sent to any DISN or GBS system without protocol translations. The output of the VTC could also be sent to the store-and-forward full motion encoders for storage and later playback.

- d. High Definition Television (HDTV):** The final video format that must be carried successfully is HDTV transmission. As standards develop to compress HDTV, the IDM/AIN demonstration project will assess and prototype HDTV. Current plans revolve around uncompressed HDTV (1.3 GB/sec) in a joint venture with the Naval Research Laboratory.

Conclusion: The IDM/AIN Service for DOD will be the cornerstone in technology development, technology assessment, and technology transfer in the area of information transmission. The outputs of the IDM/AIN Services will provide the Battlespace Commander with the ability to collect, process, and disseminate an uninterrupted flow of information. IDM/AIN effort will be the cornerstone for DoD Information Superiority.

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